

Deliverable D1.1:

Project Management and Quality Handbook

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Abstract	D1.1 summarises all procedures to be adopted by the consortium in relation to the day-to-day management of the project. The Project Management and Quality Handbook describes all PYSOLO project management procedures, including financial management, reporting and quality assurance and those for ethics issues. Relevant templates are included in the Appendix.

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History of changes

Version	Date	Modifications	Author(s)	Approved by
1	13/07/2023	Initial version	EUCORE <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Irene LIVERANI• Martina FANTINI• Francesca MANETTA• Roberto DI GIOACCHINO• Paola LOPS	POLIMI <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Marco BINOTTI All consortium members

Acronyms and abbreviations

AMGA	Annotated Model Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on Financial Statements
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
EU	European Union
EXC	Exploitation Committee
GA	Grant Agreement
IAB	Industrial Advisory Board
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
PC	Project Coordinator
PMO	Project Management Office
SC	Steering Committee
SG	Scientific Group
SyGMa	System for Grant Management (accessible through the Funding and Tenders Portal)
VAT	Value Added Tax

Acronyms used to identify consortium members

Ref.	Organisation	Acronym
B1	Politecnico di Milano	POLIMI
B2	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	CSIC
B3	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt	DLR
B4	Consorzio per la ricerca e la dimostrazione sulle energie rinnovabili	REC
B5	Politecnico di Torino	POLITO
B6	Institut National de l'Environnement Industriel et des Risques	INERIS
B7	Nova-Institut für politische und ökologische Innovation GmbH	NOVA
B8	Consorci Centre de Ciència i Tecnologia Forestal de Catalunya	CTFC
B9	EU CORE Consulting Srl	EUCORE

1. Executive Summary

The PYSOLO Project Management and Quality Handbook is meant to serve as a reference document for the day-to-day management of the project, in order to provide the consortium with a comprehensive overview of the most important internal management procedures, capitalising on EUCORE extensive experience in the management of EU funded projects.

The present version of the Handbook constitutes a simplified version for publication; the full version of the Handbook, containing the detailed description of the consortium boards and their composition, together with the envisaged approaches for the overall project management (including the handling of IPR personal data), is made available to the PYSOLO consortium only on the project shared repository, as, due to its contents, it is a sensitive document.

2. Internal management rules and procedures and quality control

2.1 Project management structures

The project management structure is organised as follows:

- 1) the **Project Coordinator** (PC)
- 2) the **Steering Committee** (SC);
- 3) the **Scientific Group** (SG);
- 4) the **Exploitation Committee** (EXC);
- 5) the **Project Management Office** (PMO);
- 6) the **Industrial Advisory Board** (IAB).

Complete details concerning the project management boards, including their function, composition and operational modalities, are included in the full version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook, available only for the consortium members.

2.3 Management procedures for organising meetings

Any member of a given consortium body should attend all relevant meetings. In case of impossibility to participate, he/she may be represented by a substitute (see CA, Section 6.2.4 for more details). Other specifications in relation to the procedures for convening and managing the meetings are contained in the full version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook posted on the project shared repository.

2.4 Quality procedures

The PYSOLO quality procedures and standards are described in the GA Annex 1 and summarised in the full version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook as, due to their confidential nature, could not be included in the present document.

2.5 Internal Communication

Ensuring effective communication among the partners represents an important key to success for the management of PYSOLO; complete information about internal communication procedures are contained in the full version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook.

3. Project financial management

The project budget is part of the PYSOLO Grant Agreement (GA Annex 2), and therefore it forms an integral part of the project's contractual documents. The Project financial management procedures represent sensitive information that are described in details in the full version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook; the current document contains only the general and already public information.

3.2 Payments

The Project Coordinator will receive by the CINEA the payments listed below:

- 1) a pre-financing payment;
- 2) two interim payments, following the approval of the periodic reports in accordance with the schedule and modalities set out in the GA Data Sheet (see point 4.2);
- 3) one payment of the balance, on the basis of the final reporting activities due at the end of the project.

After having received the funds, the Project Coordinator will then distribute the relevant amounts to the Beneficiaries, according to their individual budget allocation and the provisions introduced in the CA. All payments will be made in Euros.

3.3 Overall rules for the eligibility of costs

PYSOLO respects the overall rules for the eligibility of the costs contained in the AMGA — Annotated Model Grant Agreement; for further details please refer to the full version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook.

3.4 Direct costs

Direct costs are all the eligible costs which can be attributed directly to the project, following each Beneficiary's accounting principles and usual internal rules. The full version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook describes the main Horizon Europe eligible direct costs, providing detailed information on how to claim such costs and on the supporting documents that need to be filed to prove their eligibility.

3.5 Indirect costs

Indirect costs, also called 'overheads', are eligible costs which cannot be identified by the Beneficiary as being directly attributed to the project and they are meant to cover all the structural and support costs of an administrative, technical and logistical nature. In Horizon Europe they are equal to 25% of the eligible direct costs, excluding the costs for subcontracting and the costs of internally invoiced goods and services.

3.6 VAT costs

The eligibility of VAT depends on whether it is deductible or not as explained in the Grant Agreement and in the full version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook.

3.7 Exchange rate

In Horizon Europe all payments processed by the European Commission and the Financial Statements are in Euros. Art. 21.3 of the GA describes the rules to be applied by the Beneficiaries with accounts in currencies other than the Euro.

3.8 Keeping records

The submission of a Certificate on the Financial Statements (CFS) does NOT waive the right of the Commission to carry out its own audit which may be launched at any time and up to two years after the final payment. Therefore, the Beneficiaries must keep the project documentation for up to five years after the final payment.

3.9 How to fill in the Financial Statements

Detailed explanations and screenshots on how to fill in the Financial Statements are contained in the full version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook.

4. Reporting

Reporting constitutes a fundamental task of the project. The Grant Agreement and the full version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook contain detailed information about the reporting activities envisaged within the PYSOLO project.

4.1 Access to SyGMa and Continuous reporting

All Beneficiaries must use the continuous reporting functionality from the very start of the project in order to submit to the CINEA all the information concerning the progress of the action. For further information please refer to the full version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook.

4.2 Reporting calendar

PYSOLO foresees the “reporting periods” as detailed in the GA Datasheet and in the full version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook.

4.3 Periodic reporting activities

According to the Grant Agreement (Art. 21), the Project Coordinator has to submit three periodic reports (60 days from the end of M16, M32, M48 with financial reporting). Detailed information and step by step procedures concerning are included in the full version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook.

5. IPR Management and procedures for publications

The procedures for managing IPR and publications are strictly confidential and therefore they are accounted for only in the full version of D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook, stored in the PYSOLO shared repository.

6. Ethics Guidelines

PYSOLO, as all the other projects funded by the Horizon Europe Programme, has to comply with the ethical principles and rules provided by the European Union Law, as well as with the international and national legislations. Practical guidance for properly assessing and managing the ethical issues applicable to PYSOLO are included in the full version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook, due to their confidential contents.

7. Information Sources

The list below highlights the information sources used for the preparation of the present Handbook. A hyperlink is provided so as to allow the direct consultation of the source of interest.

- **PYSOLO Grant Agreement:** available in its most updated version on the project shared repository.
- **PYSOLO Consortium Agreement:** available on the project shared repository.
- **Annotated Model Grant Agreement Horizon Europe:** https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf
- **Horizon Europe Online Manual:** <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/display/OM/Online+Manual>
- **Periodic report template:** https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/temp-form/report/periodic-report_horizon-euratom_en.pdf
- **Funding and Tenders Online Manual:** https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/om_en.pdf
- **H2020 Ethics guidance:** https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/ethics/h2020_hi_ethics-self-assess_en.pdf

APPENDIX

The project Annexes are included in the version of the D1.1 Project Management and Quality Handbook for the exclusive use of the consortium partners, accessible through the project shared repository, which contains also the editable templates of all such documents.